

*Dopant ionic radius effects on cerium reduction:
consequences on oxygen ion based properties in
epitaxial cerium oxide thin films*

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The role of trivalent rare-earth dopants on the cerium oxidation state has been systematically studied by in-situ photoemission spectroscopy with synchrotron radiation for 10mol% rare earth doped epitaxial ceria films. It was found that dopant rare-earths with smaller ionic radius foster the formation of Ce³⁺ by releasing the stress strength induced by the cation substitution. Decreasing the dopant ionic radius from La³⁺ to Yb³⁺ the out-of-plane axis parameter of the crystal lattice decreases without introducing macroscopic defects. The high crystal quality of our films allowed us to comparatively study both the ionic conductivity and surface reactivity ruling out the influence of structural defects. The measured increase in the activation energy of films and their enhanced surface reactivity can be explained in terms of the dopant ionic radius effects on the Ce⁴⁺→Ce³⁺ reduction as a result of lattice relaxation. Such findings open new perspectives in designing ceria-based materials with tailored properties by choosing suitable cation substitution.

Introduction

Pure and doped ceria have been widely investigated for many environmental friendly applications such as *solid oxide fuel cells* (SOFCs),^{1,2} *water splitting* for hydrogen production,³ and *oxygen sensors*.⁴ Despite of the large oxygen ion conductivity of doped ceria (compare with stabilized zirconia), the electronic conductivity, arising from Ce⁴⁺ → Ce³⁺ cerium reduction, prevents its efficient use as an electrolyte.⁵ However, the same reduction process of cerium cations can be efficiently exploited in other relevant applications, such as electrodes in SOFC or water splitting catalysts for hydrogen production. In a simple fluorite crystal structure AB₂, the

physical (conductivity) and chemical properties (reactivity) of CeO_2 are both ruled by the A site-substitutions. Relevant charged defects, as oxygen vacancies and dopant ions, as well as Ce^{3+} in place of Ce^{4+} , can be induced by substitution of Ce^{4+} with a trivalent rare-earth cation (Re^{3+}).^{6,7} Gerhart-Anderson et al. first reported a non-linear ionic conductivity behavior in $\text{CeO}_2: \text{Re}_2\text{O}_3$ solid solutions with different dopant ionic radius.⁷ Bulter et al. explained this phenomenon in terms of possible dopant-vacancy interactions.⁶ Namely, defects can strongly affect both oxygen ion conductivity and surface reactivity. Indeed, for the ionic transport, activation energy can be increased either by increasing the dopant concentration⁸ or by decreasing the dopant ionic radius.⁹ The local environment can either increase or decrease the interaction between defects, depending on whether dimensionality (i.e. ion size) or electrostatic effects prevail, and, thus, affect the functional properties based on oxygen ion motion of doped ceria compounds.¹⁰ The major role of the relaxation energy in reducing the strain caused by the oxygen vacancy formation was also reported.¹¹

The oxygen non-stoichiometry caused by trivalent dopants may also shift the equilibrium potential of the reduction of Ce^{4+} to Ce^{3+} , which gives rise to electronic conductivity in reducing atmospheres and at high temperatures.¹² The importance of the $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{4+}$ redox couple on water splitting has been recently demonstrated by monitoring the Ce core level variation using in-operando photoemission spectroscopy.^{13, 14} It was reported that surface oxygen vacancies, together with electron defects were rate-determining factors for the surface reactions. In addition, Andreeva et al. reported that the best gold catalyst behavior on a doped ceria support, concurrently with higher surface concentration of Ce^{3+} , was obtained using Yb and Sm as dopants.¹⁵ This result suggested that the $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{4+}$ redox reaction rate can be altered by dopants. Most reported studies have been focused on how doping influences both physical and chemical

properties or the electrochemical performances. To the best of our knowledge, there are only few reports on systematic comparison of chemical compositions and performances for different rare-earth doped ceria systems. Literature studies on the ion conductors in form of thin films were devoted to the effect of the microstructure variation induced by the film-substrate lattice mismatch on conduction properties. Defect association/ordering and migration energy were taken into consideration to explain the reduced conductivity in case of lattice compression.^{16,17} It has also been reported that both reactivity and oxygen migration are affected by the lattice strain depending on its sign. In fact, tensile strain favors oxygen-vacancy formation,¹⁸ oxygen exchange rate,¹⁹ as well as oxygen transport.^{17, 20, 21}

However, as far as we know, effects induced by the different dopant cations on the $\text{Ce}^{3+}/\text{Ce}^{4+}$ redox couple, and therefore on the surface reactivity and electrical conductivity, were not considered so far in the case of epitaxial thin films. Therefore, we here investigate the role of the Rare earth doping on the Ce^{3+} concentration and, thus, the oxygen vacancies, and correlate the in-situ determined cerium reduction with the oxygen ion based properties both in the bulk by Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) and more on the surface by Electrochemical Strain Microscopy (ESM), thanks to the use of highly quality epitaxial films.

Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) provides a versatile approach to prepare epitaxial thin films with a precise control of chemical composition, crystallographic orientation and structural quality. As a matter of fact, when the lattice parameter mismatch between the single crystal substrate and the overlayer material is very small, a monocrystalline film can grow epitaxially on the substrate with a small number of crystallographic defects. Doped ceria films reported in literature have been grown mainly on (0001) Al_2O_3 and (0001) SiO_2 substrates, thus not providing a good lattice match with the fluorite structure of CeO_2 , as demonstrated by the

presence of spurious peaks in the x-ray diffraction spectra or large rocking curve widths^{16, 17, 22} A better lattice mismatch was obtained in the case of SrTiO₃ buffered (001) MgO²² or (110)-NdGaO₃ (NGO) substrates.^{8, 23} In particular, thanks to the good quality of the epitaxial films of Sm-doped CeO₂ with doping concentration of 10-40mol% grown on NGO substrate, we previously elucidated the intrinsic mechanisms regulating the dopant concentration effects on ion conductivity and surface reactivity. We demonstrated that highly epitaxial thin films can elucidate the intrinsic properties of the materials.⁸

In the present work, we use the same approach on highly epitaxial Re_{0.1}Ce_{0.9}O_{2- δ} (ReCO) films, with constant doping concentration (10 mol%) and variable Re dopant cations. We study Re=La, Sm, Gd and Yb, having ionic radius 1.160 Å, 1.079 Å, 1.053 Å and 0.985 Å, respectively. The 10 mol% concentration is chosen because it ensures good bulk transport properties and possible surface interaction with gas-phase water, as previously reported in the relevant literature studies.^{24, 25} The highly epitaxial nature is confirmed by in-plane and out-of-plane x-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements, including careful reciprocal space mappings. Thanks to the excellent crystallographic quality of our films the effect of structural defects can be ruled out. X-Ray Photoemission Spectroscopy (XPS) measurements by synchrotron radiation performed in-situ without exposing the samples to the air show that the Ce³⁺ concentration increases when the radius of the dopant Re decreases. This unexpected enrichment of Ce³⁺ leads us to further explore its impact on the electrochemical performances. In fact, after a careful transport and surface reactivity investigations performed by EIS and ESM, respectively, we find a lowered conductivity and an enhanced surface reactivity for the smaller dopant cation. We discuss our results based on the current theoretical studies reported in literature.^{9, 11, 26}

Through in-situ XPS using synchrotron radiation we newly we get the Ce^{3+} concentration with different Re dopant cation in ceria epitaxial films. We experimentally confirm the theoretically predicted relevance of the small Re dopant cations in facilitating the $\text{Ce}^{4+} \rightarrow \text{Ce}^{3+}$ reduction as a result of lattice relaxation.^{9, 11, 26} We comparatively study both the ionic conductivity and surface reactivity and demonstrate that the effects of the dopant ionic radius on the oxygen ion based properties can be explained in terms of the Ce^{3+} concentration which is not only significant for affecting the ionic transport process, but it can be meaningful also in boosting the surface ion exchange process.^{8, 13, 14, 23, 27}

Experimental Methods

ReCO epitaxial 300 nm thick films were grown by PLD on insulating NGO substrates at an oxygen partial pressure $\text{PO}_2=5$ Pa. A KrF excimer pulsed laser source ($\lambda = 248$ nm) operated at 10 Hz, with an energy density of 5 J/cm^2 , was used. The substrate was placed at 3.5 cm distance from the ReCO target and kept at a temperature of about 600°C .

X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis were performed both with a Rigaku D-max diffractometer using $\text{Co K}\alpha$ radiation for the standard characterization of the c-axis parameter in symmetrical configuration, and with a Philips X'Pert- XRD analytic diffractometer equipped with a four-circle cradle using a $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ source for more advanced characterizations: in particular, reciprocal space maps and azimuthal scans of the asymmetrical reflections.

X-ray photoemission spectroscopy (XPS) measurements by synchrotron radiation were carried out in-situ to avoid surface contaminations. Similar ReCO films were grown on NGO by the

PLD system of the APE-NFFA laboratory using the same optimized recipe of previous samples. Structural and electrical properties were checked on all the samples to prove their reproducibility. ReCO films were transferred without exposing to the air to the APE-beamline of Elettra synchrotron where the spectroscopic measurements were performed at 1260 eV photon excitation energy. The photoemission spectra were collected at normal emission with photons impinging at 45 degrees. The total instrumental energy resolution during XPS experiments (photons analyser) was about 0.5 eV.

Electrochemical strain microscopy (ESM) measurements were performed by a commercial atomic force microscope system (Cypher ES Environmental AFM) equipped with LabVIEW/Matlab based on the band excitation. Voltages were applied to a conductive Cr/Pt coated (Budget Sensors) AFM tip, and the bottom electrode was kept grounded by silver paint on the bottom and on the border of the sample. Air, having controlled relative humidity, was obtained by flushing dry air through a humidifier (General Electric).

Ionic conductivity of films was measured by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) using a frequency response analyzer (FRA Solartron 1260), coupled with a dielectric interface (Solartron 1296). Gold electrodes were applied in a two-electrode configuration geometry using a commercial gold paste painted onto the film surface. EIS measurements were recorded in air atmosphere in the temperature range between 600 °C and 300 °C in the frequency range between 1 MHz and 0.01 Hz. The amplitude of the applied AC voltage was 100 mV. All EIS measurements were repeated both in cooling and heating runs.

■ *Results and Discussion*

The ionic radius of the dopant cations employed in our study varied from 1.160 Å, in the case of La^{3+} , to 0.985 Å, in the case of Yb^{3+} . Such cation radius must be compared with the radius of the host ions Ce^{4+} , i.e. 0.970 Å, and reduced Ce^{3+} , i.e. 1.143 Å. It has been reported that the replacement with a larger dopant cation or the formation of Ce^{3+} should induce an enlargement of the crystal lattice due to steric effects.^{28, 29} In addition, the doping induced oxygen vacancy formation should imply lattice contraction due to electrostatic effects.^{9, 11}

To elucidate these effects we measured the structural properties by XRD measurements, as reported in Figure 1. The inset of panel 1(a) shows a typical θ - 2θ scan of ReCO (in this specific case, Re=Sm) thin films. In all cases, the absence of any other peak besides the (00 l) peaks of the ReCO phase demonstrates the single c -axis orientation of the film and the absence of spurious phases. The c -axis parameters of ReCO thin films are plotted as a function of the dopant radius in Figure 1 (a). The c -axis parameter increases from 5.40 Å for Yb-doped CeO_2 thin films to 5.47 Å for La-doped CeO_2 thin films. A lattice expansion is observed increasing the ionic radius of the dopant cation, as we move from Yb^{3+} to La^{3+} . The small in-plane lattice mismatch, from $-0.3\pm 0.2\%$ (LCO)¹⁷ to $+0.85\pm 0.2\%$ (YCO)¹⁰, between the [001] / [1-10] orthorhombic NGO pseudocubic/[1-10] orthorhombic NGO axis and the [110] axis of bulk ReCO allows the epitaxial growth of the films with a full in-plane lattice matching. This is illustrated by the reciprocal space maps in symmetrical (Figure 1(b-c)) and asymmetrical (Figure 1 (e-f)) configurations for the two extreme cases of Re cations, i.e. the smallest (YCO) and largest (LCO) cations, respectively. The low crystal structure mosaicity is confirmed by the small FWHM value of the (002) reflection: 0.2° - 0.3° for all the samples (see Supporting Information).

This epitaxial growth mode of doped ceria allows us to grow high crystallographic quality samples. The in-plane square symmetry is demonstrated by the azimuthal Φ -scan measurements reported in Figure 1(d) taken around the same asymmetric Bragg reflections of the reciprocal space maps of Figure 1 (e-f). The Φ -scans of the two extreme cases of YCO and LCO show four equally 90° spaced peaks, thus giving evidence of the in-plane square fourfold symmetry of films with $[110]$ ReCO// $[001]/[1-10]$ NGO crystal lattice directions.

Figure 1. (a) c -axis parameter of ReCO thin films vs. dopant ionic radius. A typical θ - 2θ scan of 10 mol% Sm-doped ceria film on NGO substrate is shown in the inset. (b) Reciprocal space map around the symmetrical reflections (330) of NGO substrate and (004) of YCO film. (c) Reciprocal space map around the symmetrical reflections (330) of NGO substrate and (004) of LCO film. (d) Azimuthal Φ -scan of the (-2 -2 4) asymmetrical reflections of YCO film (top panel) and LCO film (bottom panel). (e) Reciprocal space map around the asymmetrical

reflections (33-4) of NGO substrate and (-2-24) of YCO film. (c) Reciprocal space map around the asymmetrical reflections (33-4) of NGO substrate and (-2-24) of LCO film.

The full in-plane lattice matching together with the out-of-plane crystal lattice reduction with decreasing the Re ionic radius suggest the relevance of the steric effects. It's worth noting that the sign of the strain is tensile for all the ReCO films except from LCO.^{10,17} Tensile strain would favor the oxygen transport and reactivity because of the larger space available.¹⁷⁻²¹ However, the non-linear behavior of the out-of-plane crystal lattice variation reported in figure 1(a) poses the question on the Ce³⁺ formation, thus affecting the average cation size.⁹

The substitution of different Re³⁺ cations on the Ce⁴⁺ site alters the local chemistry due to different charge and size between host and dopant. Kim et al. studied oxygen vacancies preferential occupation in ZrO₂ and CeO₂ lattices. They demonstrated by NMR that oxygen vacancies preferred to sit near the host ions, i.e. Ce⁴⁺, in the case of Y-doped CeO₂, while, they stayed close to the dopant ions, i.e. Y³⁺, in the Y-doped ZrO₂. This result suggested that oxygen vacancies distribution in the fluorite crystal structure depends on both the charge and the size of the cations.³⁰ We investigate the effect of different Re dopants on changing host cations oxidation state and, in turns, the oxygen vacancies concentration. We keep the doping concentration at 10 mol% in order to eliminate the possible formation of nanosized domains that could depress the ionic conduction.^{12, 31} We apply XPS to determine ionic valence and concentration by measuring the core-level spectra of Ce and Re dopant cations.

The Ce 3*d* XPS spectra of 10 mol% La, Sm, Gd and Yb doped ceria thin films are shown in Figure 2(a). Ce 3*d* spectra contain information on both Ce⁴⁺ and Ce³⁺ oxidation states giving rise

to five peaks for each Ce $3d_{5/2}$ and Ce $3d_{3/2}$ spin-orbit coupling components,³² as reported in the Supporting Information. All films have a well-resolved Ce 3d peaks structure and allow us to use it as a “footprint” characteristic to probe the effect of the trivalent dopant radius on Ce⁴⁺ ion reduction process. Despite of the large number of contributing peaks, we keep the fitting parameters at the minimum and fix the degeneracy ratio, the binding energy and the FWHM of each component. Figure 2(a) clearly shows that a good fit can be obtained only by considering the additional contribution of Ce³⁺ components, indicated as red filled areas under the curve, reported in Figure 2(a). It can be observed that Ce⁴⁺ and Ce³⁺ coexist in all the samples with an increased Ce³⁺ contribution for the YCO film. Indeed, the relative amount of Ce³⁺ reported in Figure 2(b) shows that Ce³⁺ relative concentration increases from about 8.1 % in the LCO film to about 15.3 % in the YCO film.

Figure 2. (a) Ce 3*d* core level photoemission spectra for LCO, SCO, GCO and YCO thin films. Experimental data (open circles) are compared with the fit results (solid black lines), obtained as the envelope of the fit curve components. The solid grey line refers to the sum of all Ce⁴⁺ components and the red filled areas to the sum of all Ce³⁺ fit components. (b) X-axis histogram of Ce³⁺ concentration calculated from the corresponding red filled areas for LCO, SCO, GCO and YCO thin films reported in panel (a).

The oxidation state of the rare earth dopants is explored by measuring some representative core level photoemission spectra. Figure 3 shows La 3*d* (panel (a)), Sm 3*d* (panel (b)), Gd 4*d* (panel (c)) and Yb 4*d* (panel (d)) XPS spectra of the ReCO thin films. Despite of the spectral complexity, all of them are typical of the Re³⁺ oxidation state. A detailed rare earth elements spectra explanation is included in the Supporting Information.

Figure 3. (a) La 3*d*, (b) Sm 3*d*, (c) Gd 4*d* and (d) Yb 4*d* core level spectra of 10 mol% La, Sm, Gd and Yb doped ceria thin films.

By comparing the Ce 3*d* and Re 3*d* or 4*d* spectra, we can obtain the following useful information: i) Ce³⁺ and Ce⁴⁺ coexist for all samples. The Ce³⁺ concentration increases with decreasing the dopant ionic radius, being largest for the Yb doped ceria thin film. ii) the rare-earth cations, i.e, La, Sm, Gd as well as Yb, show only 3+ valence. The Ce³⁺ concentration is strictly related to an oxygen vacancy concentration in order to maintain electrical neutrality.³³ In fact, the ionic radii of trivalent dopants influence oxygen vacancy formation energy. By assuming the charge compensation, we find that the oxygen vacancy concentration increases from about 9.1 mol% (La) to 12.6 mol% (Yb). (see Supporting Information for details). Several effects must be considered in discussing the unexpected Ce³⁺ concentration variation. The effect of the tensile strain in favoring the oxygen kinetics and mobility due to the larger space in the lattice¹⁷⁻²¹ and the competition between the electrostatic and steric effects.^{9, 26} Since the Re dopant concentration is fixed at 10mol% and all Re dopants show only 3+ valence state, the electrostatic effect on the Re³⁺-O²⁻ energy bond should play a minor role. Despite, the effect of the tensile strain on the Ce³⁺ and oxygen vacancy formation cannot be completely ruled out, the steep increase of Ce³⁺ concentration from 10.6 mol% in the case of GCO to 15.3 mol% in the case of YCO, where the corresponding lattice mismatch variation is from +0.65% in the case of GCO to +0.85% in the case of YCO, suggests a different explanation in the Ce³⁺ formation. Following the theoretical study of Marrocchelli et al.^{9,26} we conclude on the prevalent role of ionic radius of trivalent dopants which influences the Ce³⁺ formation by favoring the structural relaxation. When Ce³⁺ is formed in the Ce⁴⁺ ion site, a certain amount of stress is accumulated in

the lattice because of Ce^{3+} larger ionic radius. Therefore, the smaller the ionic radius of the Re dopant, the lower the stress strength.

Through the XRD and XPS dataset, we note that: (i) the crystal lattice dimension changes in agreement the dimension of the ionic radius of the dopant cation, and (ii) the $\text{Ce}^{4+} \rightarrow \text{Ce}^{3+}$ reduction is favored by the smaller dopant cation thanks to its higher capability in relaxing the strain.

The effect of the structural and compositional features on the functional properties for the different rare-earth dopants is revealed by conductivity and surface reaction measurements as reported in the following. The in-plane ion conductivities are measured by EIS in dry air from 300°C to 600°C as reported in Figure 4. Two parallel strips of the Au electrodes are painted on the ReCO film surface 1 mm apart. Figure 4 (a) shows typical Nyquist plots in dry air at 500°C for ReCO thin films. Similar plots are obtained for all the samples: a single semicircle with a non-linear low frequency response. The semicircle in the complex impedance plot is due to a resistive (R) and a capacitive element (C) acting in parallel.²² The resistance obtained from the Nyquist plot decreases from 7 M Ω (La) to 2 M Ω (Yb). As it can be seen in Figure 4 (b), the conductivity at 400°C and 500°C increases as a function dopant radius in agreement with the lattice expansion revealed by XRD. For instance, at 500°C, the YCO, SCO, GCO and LCO thin films conductivity increases from 1×10^{-3} S/cm, 2.1×10^{-3} S/cm, 2.3×10^{-3} S/cm, to 5×10^{-3} S/cm. At 600°C, however, the conductivity values intercept at the same value due to their different activation energies, as estimated from Arrhenius plots. A comparison of temperature dependent ReCO thin films ion conductivity is presented in Figure 4 (c). Conductivity values reported above are larger than those reported for ceramic pellets: 1×10^{-3} S/cm for our SCO thin film vs. 3

$\times 10^{-4}$ S/cm at 400°C for microcrystalline ceramic pellets.³⁴ In addition, our films conductivity is larger than those reported for films having the same composition but grown on Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ substrates, most likely because of the better structural quality of our films.^{16,17} Indeed, Giannici et al. investigated a wide range of rare earth doped ceria microcrystalline and nanocrystalline ceramic samples.¹⁰ The measured conductivity was almost one-order magnitude larger in microcrystalline samples than nanocrystalline samples. They further separated the grain-interior and grain-boundary contribution by a detailed data analysis and concluded that the conductivity drop in nanocrystalline samples was induced by a large grain boundary density.¹⁰ We have now the possibility to directly measure grain-interior conductivity behavior by using samples in thin films form. The high crystallographic quality and unique crystal structure of our films are quite important to compare the effect of dopants on materials intrinsic electrochemical performances, ruling out the structural defects induced performance variations. We calculate the activation energy by fitting the data with the Arrhenius equation, i.e., $\sigma_{(T)} = \sigma_0/T \exp(-E_a/(K_B T))$. The dependence of activation energy (E_a) on dopant radius is shown in Figure 4 (d). E_a increases from 0.8 eV (La) to 1.2 eV (Yb), while reducing the dopant radius. The increasing trend in activation energy while decreasing the trivalent dopant ionic radius is in agreement with experimental results obtained on pellets³⁴ and theoretical calculations³⁵, even though the numerical values could be slightly different due to the fitting process. This result was explained by the lattice compression induced local cation-oxygen bond strengths reinforcement.³⁵ The E_a enhancement when decreasing the lattice constant in doped ceria thin films was also reported by Rupp et al. and explained in terms of increased migration energy, despite the role of the cation-vacancy association effects was not completely ruled out.¹⁷ Theoretical calculations of E_a with different Re cations also demonstrated that the vacancies are trapped by the lattice distortions

induced by the smaller cations thus inducing and enhancement of the activation energy.²⁶ However, the 10 mol% Yb-doped ceria film, in comparison with other doped ceria thin films, shows a larger conductivity in dry H₂ (see results in Supporting Information) than in dry air (Figure 4) in the whole temperature range. This result indicates that YCO thin film may have a more significant electronic conductivity than other samples, in agreement with its largest Ce³⁺ concentration observed by XPS (Figure 2).

Figure 4. (a) Nyquist plots of ReCO films at 500 °C in air. (b) Conductivity plot versus dopant radius for 400°C, 500°C and 600°C. (c) Arrhenius plot of ReCO films involved in this study together with the linear fit. (d) Dopant radius dependence of the activation energy.

Based on the well-established role of the Ce³⁺ in favoring the surface oxygen exchange process,^{8,14} we measured our ReCO films with different Ce³⁺ concentrations by ESM to

investigate the role of rare-earth dopants on the surface reaction. ESM is a local electrochemical technique based on Scanning Probe Microscopy (SPM), which can provide direct information on electrochemical processes by using the SPM tip as a moving electrode.³⁶ In our present case, i.e. wet/ambient air condition, when the applied voltage is larger than the water splitting overpotential, the hydrolysis group can be generated or annihilated by the following reaction:

The movement of the hydrolysis group results in a localized strain beneath the tip, which is responsible for the surface displacement.⁸ Note that the critical potential recorded in ESM measurements to activate the reaction should be larger than the standard reaction overpotential, because the finite conductivity can give rise to the potential drops inside the material.³⁶

A typical topography image of a ReCO film surface measured before the ESM measurements is presented in Figure 5 (a). The sample is very smooth with no visible features on the surface. The mean square surface roughness of about 0.2 ± 0.05 nm is detected. The very smooth surfaces of our films allow performing reproducible ESM measurements. A well-defined hysteresis loop can be observed for all ReCO films in Figure 5(b). Balke et al. interpreted the ESM hysteresis loop by a reaction-diffusion process. The area under the loop is directly proportional to the change in ion concentration induced during the voltage cycle.³⁷ We compare the loop area for different ReCO thin films. The loop area reaches a maximum value for the Yb doped ceria thin film (YCO) and has a minimum for La doped ceria thin film (LCO). This implies that Yb/La doped ceria thin films may have the maximum/minimum hydrolysis group exchange during the measurements. Successively, in order to investigate the relative humidity effect on the surface reactivity, we focus on the YCO thin film, as shown in Figure 5 (c). For the YCO thin film the

loop area increases linearly with relative humidity, suggesting a water vapour assisted surface reaction process.

In order to further discriminate surface reaction and migration process, we perform First Order Reversible Curve (FORC) measurements on YCO thin film.³⁸ Assuming that the on-site ion transport process is negligibly affected by the applied DC bias variation in our investigated voltage range, the observed variations in the ESM signal can reasonably be related to the surface reactions; this is in agreement with earlier observations in ionic oxide systems probed by FORC.³⁸ Figure 5 (d) shows the fitted loop area behavior for YCO thin films. We can note that the loop area, i.e. ion concentration change, depends linearly on the driving force. The slope reveals important information on the transport process after the activation of the surface reaction. We note that the reaction is faster (larger slope) in the wet air, i.e. 60% RH and 90% RH, than the dry air, i.e. 4% RH. This is in agreement with reaction (1): water vapor shifts the reaction equilibrium to the right and, as a consequence, a larger hydrolysis group exchange could be induced during the measurement cycle.

Findings from the ESM and FORC measurements suggest that water-splitting process is observed for Re doped ceria thin films. The surface reactivity shows a clear dependence on the dopant ionic radius. The maximum surface reactivity is found for YCO thin film. The increase in reaction velocity with humidity confirms its water vapor assisted reaction nature (1).

Figure 5. (a) SPM topography on a $800 \times 800 \text{ nm}^2$ square area of 10 mol% Sm-doped ceria film on NGO substrate (b). ESM hysteresis loops of Re doped ceria thin films at 60 % RH at ambient conditions. (c) Set of ESM hysteresis loops of 10 mol% Yb doped ceria thin film measured in the humidity dependent chamber with different relative humidity. (d) FORC measurement results for Yb doped ceria thin film at air with different relative humidity.

■ Conclusions

Despite of the large amount of literature on the role of cation substitutions in the transport properties of doped ceria,¹⁷ further understanding on the cation dimension effects on the charge balance and, in turn, on the electrochemical properties is still needed. Indeed, many theoretical studies are reported in literature^{9, 17-21,26,} but a comprehensive experimental study of both the ion conductivity and surface reaction, together with the detailed investigation of both the structural properties and the chemical defects concentration, was still missing especially in the case of

epitaxial thin films. We here use high quality epitaxial films of CeO₂ doped with trivalent rare-earth cations (Re=La, Sm, Gd and Yb) to study the correlation among dopant radius, oxidation state and oxygen ion based performances. Supported by XRD measurements and SPM surface analysis, we conclude that the grown films are well controlled in surface roughness and crystal orientation. Hence, we can use them for studying the electrochemical performances in terms of surface reactivity as well as ion conductivity, ruling out the influence of structural defects.

The lattice distortion can be tuned when proper trivalent dopants are inserted in the fluorite lattice. We find that the largest dopant (La³⁺) induces lattice expansion, while, on the contrary, smaller dopant (Yb³⁺) gives rise to lattice compression, while keeping the full in-plane lattice matching thanks to the very low mismatch with NGO substrate. Different Re cations also affect the chemical defect concentration. In fact, XPS results reveal that the Ce⁴⁺ and Ce³⁺ valence states coexist on the surface of all the doped thin films, with the Ce³⁺ concentration increasing from about 8.1% in LCO to about 15.3% in YCO. This is quite surprising, since we would expect an equal Ce³⁺ concentration due to the fixed chemical composition. Based on published theoretical work^{34,37}, combining the XRD with XPS results, we suggest that a smaller Re dopant radius favors the local structural relaxation after Ce⁴⁺→Ce³⁺ reduction process.

The effect of the trivalent dopant on the ion conductivity measured by EIS is manifold: (1) the conductivity increases almost linearly as a function of the dopant radius below 500°C. (2) the activation energy increases while decreasing the trivalent dopant radius. (3) a more pronounced electronic conductivity in the case of YCO is also found as a consequence of the highest Ce³⁺ concentration.

At the same time, the smallest dopant ions size in the case YCO films enhances the surface ion exchange activity with respect to the other samples, measured by the ESM. The YCO films surface ion exchange activity increases while increasing the relative humidity. These results directly support the idea that Ce^{3+} species in YCO are responsible for water molecules-lattice interaction, similarly to what previously reported on pure ceria.¹⁴

From the whole set of experimental data, we can conclude that dopant ionic radius can affect the Ce^{3+} concentration by favouring local structural relaxation. Indeed, a smaller dopant cation as Yb^{3+} can induce a larger displacement from the nearest neighboring ions due to its size, thus further promoting cerium ion reduction process in the lattice. This can explain the dopant ion size dependent Ce^{3+} variation, as shown by XPS measurements, and, in turn, the ionic conductivity and surface reactivity results obtained by EIS and ESM. In conclusion, our study provides a framework for the design of ceria-based materials with better functional properties for possible environmental friendly applications. Specific theoretical investigations are required for further understanding the microscopic mechanism behind our experimental findings.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

X-Ray diffraction reciprocal space mapping; X-ray Photoemission Spectroscopy Detailed Analysis; Rare earth elements spectra analysis as well as the EIS measurements in dry H_2 can be found in the associated content. Those materials are available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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N.Y. designed the project and participated to the whole work from thin film preparation to data analysis; C.A contributed in design the project and directed the research; P.O grew the in-situ samples and performed detailed XRD measurements; P.O., P.T. and G.R. optimized the experimental set-up for the in-situ XPS experiment. N.Y., C.A., P.O., P.T. and G.R. designed and carried-out the synchrotron XPS measurements within the NFFA project and contributed to the results interpretation; C.A. performed the XPS analysis; E. Di B. and S. L. performed and analyzed the EIS measurements with the contribution of N.Y.; V.F and G. B. participated in thin films design; N.Y., A. I. and S.K. settled and participated in ESM experiments design and data analyses. All the authors discussed the results, and fully revised the manuscript.

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